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GUIDING UNIVERSITIES TO DEVELOP ENGAGING K-12 OUTREACH PROGRAMS

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ABSTRACT

At the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), the student learning experience is informed by a "Mens et Manus"-style pedagogy with hands-on, learning-by-doing activities that complement the many facets of engineering education that happen around the Institute. However, this mindset is not only relegated to the engineering disciplines as courses in the sciences, mathematics, humanities, arts, and social sciences also implement tenets of this style of instruction. As a result, the permeation of this learning-by-doing spirit also shines through in the activities and initiatives that take place outside of the classroom. For example, MIT programs like Global Teaching Labs (GTL), MIT International Science & Technology Initiatives (MISTI), the Abdul Latif Jameel World Education Lab (J-WEL), and STEAM Camps give MIT students the opportunity to teach and share MIT's unique approach to education with partner schools around the world.

Although MIT's main focus is college-level education, there is a great understanding of the importance and growing interest towards transforming and enhancing K-12 level education at both the administration and faculty levels. Developing new

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resources but also by attempting to transmit MIT's core values to the K-12 system, MIT has a long history of K-12 outreach programs, with a particular focus in both STEM and STEAM education. Our proposed workshop focuses on how universities and institutions of higher education can utilize the resources and talent within their institutions to develop outreach programs and initiatives aimed at engaging K-12 learners and educators. As citadels of both culture and knowledge, universities are in the best position to transform and have lasting impacts on both educators and younger students. In our workshop, we will discuss our approaches for how to create offerings that are initiated by university faculty, students, and staff. By taking participants through a design thinking exercise devised to have academics consider deeply how the work they do can contribute meaningfully to the experiences of a K-12 student.

With a strong K-12 community, we have found that many groups can collaborate to meet the needs of different types of learners. For example, MIT's pK-12 community often finds diverse ways to work together in new efforts, stemming from a recognition of various groups' areas and levels of expertise. This community of practice pulls participation from multiple departments, labs, centers, and student-created groups, stretching across faculty, staff, and both the undergraduate and graduate populations. Similarly to the definition of community of practice by Wenger (1998), the members of our K-12 community share similar values and beliefs about learning and about finding ways to continue to refine and improve what we do in benefit of learners and educators. There is even more to discuss regarding the ways that higher education institutions can be a positive resource within our current world climate. With the massive impact that the spread of COVID-19 has had around the globe, we, as centers of learning, have all had to make significant modifications to the ways that we interact with learners, including the K-12 educators and students who have all been relegated to their homes throughout 2020. Two additional efforts that we plan to reference include an adaptation of a week-long in-person set of events that transformed into a remote, six-week seminar focused on designing learning experiences and a collection of curated resources for K-12, higher education, and workforce learners meant as a rapid response to the need for online resources during the pandemic. Both were modified and adapted over the course of a few weeks and can serve as examples to demonstrate how a university can continue to have positive and engaging effects on K-12 education from a distance.

In our proposed 80-minute workshop, we intend to take participants through a process that will explore their own work and consider pathways that can be taken to make stronger connections with those who work within K-12 contexts. Relevant questions discussed will include:

- What existing efforts to connect to K-12 populations take place at your universities?
- How does the K-12 outreach community come together at your institution (if at all)?
- And what are the things you think you could be doing that you're not?

We will discuss our approach for creating opportunities and also for connecting both university students with faculty and staff to support diverse communities of learners as well as the underlying motivations for why an institution of higher learning may want to pursue connecting with younger learners at all. Along with this we will bring examples of both what has worked and not worked so well in our experiences with outreach. In lieu of the current COVID-19 situation, we also plan to address and advise on practices we have tested for creating engaging remote online learning experiences. We hope during this workshop, participants will share ideas that have sparked their interest and join in a discussion on how universities can come together as a force in engaging with K-12 education. Expected learning outcomes will include learning about our framework for identifying and supporting existing university K-12 outreach programs as well as the development of strategies to foster stronger relationships between universities and K-12 learners. Ideal participants will include faculty members, university leaders, and policymakers but teachers and students may also find benefits from attending.